

INFLUENCE OF DIPLOMACY TO LANGUAGE CHANGE

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Gid hamrohligi Madaniyatlararo muloqot va

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Annotation: This research intends to present the position of English language in terms of its diplomacy. The method that is deployed in this research mixed, i.e. qualitative and quantitative, where the survey and interviews were performed with the individuals.

Key words: Diplomatic Language, English, Experience, Reflection.

The most famous language is English among the diplomatic languages and it is considered as the first and foremost choice for elite and masses. English is known by 1.1 billion people as foreign or second language and it outnumbers the native speakers of Europeans in addition to the native speakers of 375 million. The language of prestige and power is considered English as it has become a global language and it also plays a role of international gatekeeper to economic as well as social progress alongside a huge tolerance for linguistic variations. English is currently dominated a language of a world and this matter is undoubted. In majority of the international organizations, this is playing working or an official part. Since World War II, French has been replaced by English as diplomacy's lingua franca et all. There is major significance of the usage of the language in diplomacy, there is no simplicity of language, it is responsible for transmitting thoughts, or it is considered as communication instrument, it is also considered as diplomatic vocation's essence, from our profession's early beginnings. There had to be trained and educated first envoys of mediaeval Dubrovnik consuls, Roman legates, Egyptian pharaohs, etc. The language allows to overcome the differences and help in forming an integrative environment. The issue of communication between individuals who belong to distinct mother tongues can be overcome by various ways. But there is no ideal way. There can be a solution which can be interlocutors who speak other's language. There can be problem due to: it may be complex for applying in multilateral diplomacy, possible political

implications are present, there may be no adequate knowledge of the language, one possesses significant and immediate benefit and the other makes concession. A third, neutral language is used by both sides as it is a second possibility. Full linguistic knowledge as well as control is possessed by neither side which leads to the probable consequential misunderstandings as it may be a potential problem. However, due to its political benefits, there is frequent application of this method in international practice. There is also a wide usage of a third formula which is to use interpreters, especially, at high political level, for negotiations or in multilateral diplomacy- not because of the equity's reasons, but due to the fact that foreign languages are not spoken often by statesmen and politicians. To understand the use of the English as a language of diplomacy, this research was conducted. Previous researches that have analyzed the language as diplomatic has not considered the experiences of the individuals who have travelled or reside at places where English was the major language. Thereby, using the reflective model, this research intends to present the position of English language in terms of its diplomacy.

English and Diplomasy. Among the diplomatic languages English is the most popular; it is the first choice amongst the masses and the elite alike. In addition to the 375 million native speakers, it has been suggested that 1.1 billion people know English as a second or foreign language, outnumbering the native speakers by 3 to 1. 51 % of Europeans speak English as their native or as a foreign language. With a great tolerance for linguistic variations, English as a global language has become the language of power and prestige and thereby an international gatekeeper to social and economic progress. The current dominance of English as a world language is undisputed. It plays an official or working role in most international organizations.

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